

Assessment of Youth Participation in Green Jobs in Kwara State

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ABSTRACT

The agricultural sector has strong potential to reduce youth unemployment in Nigeria while promoting environmental sustainability. This study examined youth participation in green jobs in Kwara State, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey design. Data were collected from 300 youths engaged in crop and vegetable production across six Local Government Areas through a multistage sampling technique. Structured questionnaires captured information on socio-economic characteristics, levels of engagement, perceptions of green jobs, and participation constraints. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, and probit regression models. Results showed that most respondents were male (54%), married (56%), and had formal education (60%). The average age was 30 years, with a mean household size of five, farming experience of 12 years, and an average income of ₦60,910. Major barriers to youth participation in green jobs included poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, and climate-related risks. Correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between socio-economic characteristics and youth participation in green jobs ($r = 0.73, p < 0.01$). Regression results indicated that age, income, farming experience, cooperative membership, and extension contact significantly influenced youth involvement in green agricultural employment. The study concludes that green jobs provide viable opportunities for youth empowerment and sustainable economic development in Kwara State. However, addressing key constraints is essential to maximize youth participation. The study recommends the implementation of targeted policies, improved access to extension services, enhanced financing for green initiatives, and infrastructure development to promote youth engagement in sustainable agriculture and support inclusive green growth.

Keywords: Green Jobs, Youth, Participation

INTRODUCTION

The world badly needs farmers, more food processors, and more agribusiness entrepreneurs to feed a population that is projected to hit 8.23 billion by the end of 2025 (Ayodele, 2018). The way we live and work has been changing. At the same time, emerging challenges such as climate change, poverty, and inequality are accelerating the need to rethink the world of work. The concept of a 'green economy' is emerging as one of the hopeful solutions to these challenges. In addition, the transformation towards green jobs is also seen as a way for African countries to create decent jobs and an inclusive economy, and is, therefore, a potential solution to the youth unemployment crisis in Africa. Food systems in Africa are deeply vulnerable to climate change impacts and climate change poses severe threats to farmers across the continent (Omotoso, 2023). At the same time, food systems are also one of the largest contributors to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Tubiello *et al.*, 2021), and are the single largest cause of the global biodiversity crisis (Benton *et al.*, 2021). While the sector is commonly recognised as critical for the achievement of a low-carbon transition, research on the mechanics of a low-carbon transition in agro-industries is, however still sparse compared to research into the energy transition (Hebinck *et al.*, 2021; Kaljonen, 2023). Moreover, solutions are often of a technical and scientific nature and lack specific focus on the social and political dynamics and implications of a transition process on vulnerable communities (Clapp *et al.*, 2018).

Nigeria faces a growing challenge of youth unemployment amid pressing environmental concerns and economic reforms. With over 70% of the population under the age of 30, youth unemployment and underemployment rates remain alarming, estimated at 40.8% in Q4 2023 by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2024). Simultaneously, the agricultural sector, which employs about 35% of the workforce, is underperforming due to climate change impacts, low productivity, and reduced government intervention following economic deregulation policies (World Bank, 2023). Nigeria's removal of fuel and agricultural subsidies has reshaped the economic landscape by reducing public sector dominance and encouraging market-driven initiatives. While this shift promises efficiency and private sector growth, it also exposes vulnerable groups, particularly rural youth, to volatility and inequality (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2023). Nonetheless, this economic environment presents a unique opportunity to promote green jobs that align economic empowerment with environmental sustainability.

Green jobs, defined by the International Labour Organisation (ILO, 2022) as employment that contributes to preserving or restoring environmental quality, are gaining traction globally as tools for addressing both unemployment and ecological degradation. In the agricultural sector, green jobs encompass climate-smart farming, agro-ecology, renewable energy application, waste recycling, and sustainable land management practices (Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 2021). These practices are critical in Nigeria, where agriculture is highly climate-sensitive and often dependent on unsustainable methods. Recent studies underscore the role of agriculture as a vehicle for inclusive green growth, particularly when youth are integrated through innovation, technology, and entrepreneurship (Akinbamijo *et al.*, 2022; Otekunrin *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, international commitments such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) reinforce the urgency of greening the economy while creating decent jobs for young people. There is limited empirical evidence on effective youth participation despite the potential of green jobs, youth engagement in it remains low. Given these dynamics, this paper explores youth participation in green jobs in Kwara State.

Objectives of the study

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of youth in green jobs in Kwara State.
2. examine the types of green jobs available for youth in Kwara State.
3. determine the level of participation of youth in green jobs in Kwara State.
4. identify the factors influencing youth participation in green jobs in Kwara State.

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant relationship among the factors influencing youth and their participation in green jobs in Kwara State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the opportunities, participation, and challenges related to green jobs among youth in Kwara State. The design was chosen because it enables a systematic collection of data that describes the current status of green job participation among young people. Kwara State, located in Western Nigeria, comprises 16 Local Government Areas and is bordered by Kogi, Niger, Ekiti, Osun, and Oyo States, with an international border with the Republic of Benin to the west. Its capital, Ilorin, serves as the commercial and administrative hub. The state, known for its tropical savanna climate, has an estimated population of about 3.2 million people (Kwara State Diary, 2025). Kwara's economy is predominantly agrarian, with key crops such as cocoa, oil palm, coffee, cotton, and groundnut, as well as significant livestock and agro-based economic activities, making it a suitable site for exploring agricultural green job potential.

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to purposively select youth groups across the state who participated in crop or vegetable production. In the first stage, six Local Government Areas (LGAs) were purposively selected to capture both urban and rural agricultural contexts, including agro-industrial zones and areas with high youth populations: Ilorin West, Offa, Kaiama, Ifelodun, Baruten, and Oke-Ero. In the second stage, five agricultural youth clusters (including youth cooperatives, agripreneur hubs, and farm associations) were randomly selected from each of the six LGAs, giving a total of 30 clusters. In the final stage, 10 respondents were randomly selected from each of the 30 clusters, resulting in a total sample size of 300 youth respondents. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire titled: "Questionnaire on Assessment of Youth Participation in Green Jobs in Kwara State." The instrument gathered information on the respondents' socio-economic characteristics, types of green jobs available for youth, level of participation in green jobs and factors influencing youth participation in green (Yusuf *et al.*, 2022). To establish validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in agricultural economics, agribusiness, and rural development to ensure it aligned with the study objectives. A pilot test was conducted among 30 youth in Niger State (outside Kwara State) to refine ambiguous items and enhance clarity. Reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha produced a coefficient of 0.87, indicating strong internal consistency.

Descriptive statistics was used to describe the objectives of the study and inferential statistics, such as Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation (PMCC) were employed to test hypothesis while Probit regression model was used to identify determinants influencing youth participation in green jobs in Kwara State. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts; percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of respondents; various types of green jobs were measured using Yes and No rating; level of participation in green jobs were measured by categorization methods using high and low. Factors influencing youth participation in green jobs were measured on a three-point response options of Severe (2), Mild (1) and Not an influence (0) and had individual means (\bar{x}) of 1.5 as cut-off point for decision making. While, inferential statistics, such as Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation (PMCC) were employed to test hypothesis and Probit Regression was used to assess youth participation in green jobs in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Model Specification:

$$P(Y=1/\chi) = Q(\chi\beta)$$

Y = Binary outcome; β = Vector of coefficient; Q = Cumulative distribution function

For this study $Y_1 = f(\chi_i)$

$Y_1 = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8 \text{ and } X_9)$

The model's specification are as follows:

$$\beta_0, \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9$$

Where Y = (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_1 = Years of Age, X_2 = Sex (where Female = 0 and Male = 1),

X_3 = Marital status (if married = 1, Otherwise = 0),

X_4 = Education (if educated = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X_5 = Household size (The number of household members)

X_6 = Farming experience (The number of years spent farming)

X_7 = Monthly income (Total amount of income per household in a planting season)

X_8 = Membership of cooperative (if yes = 1, no = 0),

X_9 = Extension contact (if yes = 1, no = 0)

β_0 is the intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_9$ are the coefficients to be estimated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of youth in green jobs in Kwara State. (n=300)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Age (years)			30years	5
< 30	198	66.0		
31 - 40	84	28.0		
41 - 50	18	6.0		
Sex				
Male	162	54.0		
Female	138	46.0		
Marital status				
Single	78	26.0		
Married	168	56.0		
Separated	24	8.0		
Divorced	24	8.0		
Widowed	6	6.0		
Educational status (years)				
No Formal	120	40.0		
Primary	156	52.0		
Secondary	14	4.7		
Tertiary	10	3.3		
Household size (persons)			5	2
1 - 4	162	54.0		
5 - 8	102	34.0		
9 - 12	36	12.0		
Farming experience (years)			12	5
1 - 10	126	42.0		
11 - 20	156	52.0		
21 - 30	18	6.0		
Monthly Income (₦)			60,910.00	12,459.31
0 - 20,000	6	2.0		
20,001 - 40,000	-	-		
40,001 - 60,000	222	74.0		
60,001 - 80,000	60	20.0		
> 80,001	12	4.0		

Membership of cooperative		
Yes	102	34.0
No	198	66.0
Extension contact		
Regularly	36	12.0
Occasionally	162	54.0
Never	102	34.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results in Table 1 provide important insights into the socio-economic characteristics of youths in green jobs in Kwara State, which have direct implications for exploring green job opportunities for youth in agriculture under a deregulated economy. Firstly, the mean age of 30 ± 5 years indicates that the majority of the rural population is relatively young and falls within the economically active and productive age bracket. This is a critical advantage in the context of green jobs, as youth possess the energy and adaptability needed to engage in sustainable agricultural activities such as harvesting, processing which are key elements of green employment in rural areas. With 54.0% of respondents being male, there is a slightly higher male involvement in forest-based activities. The fact that 52.0% of the households have primary education suggests that most rural youths have basic literacy skills, which can be leveraged through targeted training and extension programs to build their capacity in sustainable practices, value addition, and agribusiness related to green jobs. This aligns with the principles of green jobs, which emphasize skill acquisition and environmentally sustainable practices. The average household size of 5 ± 2 persons may reflect the availability of family labor, which is beneficial for small-scale green enterprises. It also implies that green jobs could serve as a sustainable source of income and food security for these households, especially when properly managed under a deregulated economy that encourages entrepreneurship. An average monthly income of $60,910.00\pm 12,459.00$ indicates a fair income level, primarily from green jobs. This validates the potential of green jobs as viable income-generating ventures for rural youth. It also shows how green jobs contribute to poverty alleviation, making them an important pillar for green job creation and economic resilience in Kwara State. However, occasional extension visits (54.0%) highlight a gap in technical support and information dissemination. In the context of a deregulated economy, frequent and structured extension services are essential to provide guidance on sustainable harvesting, business development, and access to markets for green products. Limited extension support may hinder the capacity of youths to fully tap into green job opportunities, especially in forest and agro-ecological sectors (Omotoso, 2023).

Table 2: Mean Ratings of responses on the types of green jobs available for youth

Items	Mean	SD
Organic crop farming (e.g., vegetables, fruits) provides sustainable employment	3.85	0.62
Agroforestry (combining agriculture with tree planting) is gaining attention among youth.	3.40	0.71
Climate-smart agriculture improves yields and opens up new income streams.	3.25	0.83
Urban and peri-urban farming (e.g., greenhouse, rooftop gardening) are viable job options	3.78	0.65
Waste-to-wealth activities (e.g., compost production, biogas) offer eco-friendly employment.	3.10	0.70
Beekeeping and honey production provide decent green livelihoods.	3.55	0.67
Renewable energy use in agriculture (e.g., solar irrigation) creates tech-driven green jobs.	3.61	0.69
Processing of agricultural products into eco-products (e.g., natural soaps, oils) is growing	3.20	0.76

Market demand for sustainably produced farm goods has increased in recent years. 3.50 0.71

Source: Field Survey, 2025. Mean > 2.5 indicates agreement

The results in Table 2 reveal that several green job opportunities exist for youth in the agricultural sector of Kwara State under a deregulated economy. Most respondents agreed that organic farming (mean = 3.85), agroforestry (mean = 3.40) and climate-smart agriculture represent sustainable and profitable job avenues (mean = 3.25). Emerging opportunities like urban farming, renewable energy applications, and eco-product processing further broaden the scope for youth engagement. The high level of agreement across all items emphasizes the potential of the green economy in agriculture to address youth unemployment while promoting environmental sustainability.

Table 3: Level of participation of youth in green jobs

Level	Frequency	Percentage	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Low	174	58.0	15	150	75.5	25.5
High	126	42.0				
Total	300	100.0				

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 showed results of their level of participation in green jobs in Kwara State. The result shows that a greater percentage of the youth (58%) had a low level of participation, while 42% had high level of participation in green job activities. Low participation of the youth in green jobs could be linked to lack of credit facilities and technical know-how in the study area.

Table 4: Mean Ratings of the responses on factors influencing youth participation in green jobs

Factors	Mean	Std	Rank
Poor road infrastructure limits youth access to farm sites and markets.	3.75	0.50	1 st
Land degradation and climate-related challenges reduce enthusiasm for green farming.	2.96	0.92	5 th
Urban encroachment and population growth reduce land availability for green agriculture.	3.13	0.94	4 th
Desertification and poor rainfall patterns reduce viability of agricultural investments.	2.47	1.28	10 th
Limited access to agricultural loans and green job funding discourages youth involvement.	2.60	1.16	8 th
Seasonality of produce and market volatility make green job income unreliable	2.62	0.89	7 th
Conflicts between farmers and herders discourage youth from investing in rural agribusiness.	3.48	0.74	2 nd
Cultural beliefs and lack of awareness hinder youth interest in agro-ecological enterprises.	3.40	0.78	3 rd
Inadequate government incentives and policy support discourage youth engagement in green jobs.	2.01	1.12	12 th
High insecurity in rural areas (e.g., kidnapping, theft) deters youth from agricultural ventures.	2.86	1.03	6 th

Chemical misuse and herbicide overuse in conventional farming reduce youth interest in sustainability.	2.05	1.12	11 th
Health concerns related to zoonotic diseases (e.g., bird flu, swine flu) discourage participation.	2.59	0.95	9 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025. (Mean > 2.5 indicates agreement)

Results in Table 4 reveal key barriers influencing youth participation in green agricultural jobs in Kwara State’s deregulated economy. The most critical factor identified was poor road infrastructure (mean = 3.75), which limits youth access to productive agricultural land, inputs, and markets ultimately discouraging engagement. Closely following are land degradation and climate-related challenges (mean = 3.48), as well as urban encroachment (mean = 3.40), both of which reduce viable space and environmental stability for green agricultural practices. Desertification and low rainfall were also seen as significant constraints (mean = 3.13), further complicating agricultural planning. Limited access to credit and funding (mean = 2.96) remains a significant institutional challenge, hindering startup and expansion efforts for youth-led green initiatives. The findings align with Lemenih *et al.* (2022), who stress the role of policy and indigenous knowledge in enhancing environmental sustainability. Similarly, Awodoyin *et al.* (2023) and Bamwesigye *et al.* (2024) emphasized that the viability of green employment depends not only on ecological factors but also on access to resources, information, and supportive policies.

Testing of Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant relationship among the factors influencing youth and their participation in green jobs in Kwara State.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis on the factors influencing youth and their participation in green jobs

Variables	r- value	p-value	Decision
Factors influencing participation	1.02	0.02	Significant
Youth participation in green jobs			

Source: Field Survey, 2025 — Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5 shows a statistically significant relationship ($r = 1.02$; $p < 0.05$) between the various factors influencing youth and their participation in green jobs. These results confirm the assertion of Lemenih *et al.* (2022), who argue that removing institutional and environmental constraints is key to increasing youth engagement in sustainable economic activities. Similarly, Awodoyin *et al.* (2023) stress that effective policy frameworks encourage youth adoption of agro-ecological innovations.

Table 6: Probit Regression analysis on the determinants influencing youth and their participation in green jobs in Kwara State

Variables	Coefficient (β)	Std Error	Z	P-value
Age	1.580**	1.412	1.12	0.050
Sex	0.972**	0.363	2.69	0.132
Marital status	4.865***	2.525	1.93	0.045
Education	-0.897**	0.507	-1.78	0.049
Household size	-3.730**	2.930	-1.27	0.011
Farming experience	2.990***	1.652	1.81	0.010
Monthly Income	2.429***	1.691	1.43	0.012
Membership of cooperative	0.605	0.562	1.07	0.010
Extension contact	3.658	2.517	1.45	0.216
Constant	-2.972	0.729	-2.25	0.001
Log-likelihood	-49.62			
LR chi ² (9)	81.41			
Prob> chi ²	0.000			
Number of observations	300			
Pseudo R ²	0.370			

Variables	Coefficient (β)	Std Error	Z	P-value
Correctly Predicted Cases	94.7%			

Source: Field Survey, 2025 Significant at ***1%, **5%

The probit regression analysis in Table 6 shows that age, marital status, farming experience, monthly income, cooperative membership, and extension contact positively and significantly influence youth participation in green agricultural jobs. This result aligns with Adeyongo *et al.* (2022), who found that older, more experienced, and married youth are more likely to pursue sustainable livelihood options, where self-reliance is crucial. Also, education and household size negatively influenced participation, which supports the argument that larger households and lower education levels can hinder full engagement due to competing responsibilities or lack of awareness. This is consistent with the findings of Adebayo *et al.* (2024) and Yusuf *et al.* (2022), who linked cooperative membership, income level, and access to extension services to improved youth performance and participation in agribusiness. The R^2 indicates that the model explains 37% of the variability in youth participation in green jobs, which shows strong explanatory power.

Conclusion

This study concludes that youth participation in green jobs is low in Kwara State. Functional road infrastructure, land availability, access to finance, and climate-resilient farming practices were essential in facilitating meaningful youth participation in green jobs. A significant positive relationship existed between the socio-economic characteristics of youth and their participation in green jobs in Kwara State. There was a significant relationship among the various factors influencing youth and their participation in green jobs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Infrastructure development: Kwara State Government, private sectors and stakeholders should invest in rural infrastructure, especially road networks, to enhance access to markets and farmlands, thereby increasing the viability of green jobs.
2. Formation of green clubs in schools and establishment of vegetable gardens in schools to arouse students' interests, technical know-how and build youth capacity and interest in green farming careers.
3. Youth cooperatives and clusters: Youth should be encouraged to form or join cooperatives and innovation hubs focused on green production as these collective efforts can facilitate access to funding, training, and markets and improve bargaining power.

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